

EDITORIAL**Preface to the first issue of Ecocycles**

On behalf of the Committee of the European Ecocycles Society (ECyS) we are pleased to announce the publication of the inaugural issue of *Ecocycles*, our Society's scientific journal. *Ecocycles* has been many months in the making: the Committee of ECyS became aware of the wide interest in the subject during the foundation of the Society and felt that a committed journal would be able to bring together the ideas of a broad academic community.

Ecological cycles are the various self-regulating processes that recycle the earth's limited resources (water, carbon, nitrogen, and other elements) that are essential to sustain life. The Eco Cycle strategy is based on these processes and is aimed at bringing about a society with non-toxic and resource-efficient cycles. Understanding how local cycles fit into global ones is essential to make the best possible management decisions in order to maintain ecosystem health and productivity for now and the future.

Our Society has been created by researchers studying these cycles with the goal to promote exchange of scientific ideas in order to further scientific collaboration. We will try to engage a broad audience of researchers, scholars and practitioners in order to bring them together, coordinate their research in the area of ecological cycles, exchange information, publish their works, and award prizes paying special attention to support and encourage contributors starting their careers, as well as to publish the work of established and senior scholars from Europe and beyond. The main task of the journal is to serve as a medium for exhibiting the practical dimension of how ecological cycles function and to publish results of academic research, case studies, book reviews and commentary on issues and ideas on the relationship between ecological cycles and the society.

The area of ecological cycles became an appealing field of study in the early 2000s and has attracted growing interest since then. It soon became obvious that the continuously rising number of researchers active in the field needs a scientific journal to distribute their findings. Therefore, *Ecocycles* will publish peer-reviewed, original research and review articles focused on the science of ecological cycles to address unique areas of current and emerging environmental and ecological aspects, covering a broad range of issues and focusing on why they matter for a particular environmental point of view. The full papers are available on-line: <http://www.ecocycles.eu/ojs/index.php/Ecocycles/index>.

In addition, the journal may publish special issues on various topics related to ecological cycles, conference reports, letters to the editors, book reviews, announcements of scientific meetings, etc. The field covered in the Journal is very wide (Table 1). We know that specific journals exist

Table 1. Areas covered by *Ecocycles*

Agriculture and fisheries
Climatology and climate change
Cultural heritage
Ecological cycles: general considerations
Ecotoxicology
Environmental economics and environmental sociology
Environmental education and pedagogy
Environmental engineering
Environmental geology
Environmental law and legislation
Environmental pollution, protection and management and solid waste management - (phytoremediation)
Food safety
Forestry
Genetically modified organisms
Geoinformatics
Industrial structure and urban planning (including urban agriculture)
Natural resources management
Nature conservation
Plant, animal and human ecology (invasive and migratory species)
Regional development
Rural development
Social marketing, communication and media management
Soil conservation
Soil-plant interactions
Sustainable energy production
Transport and traffic
Viticulture and oenology
Waste minimization, management, and pollution prevention
Water resources and wastewater management
Wildlife management and rehabilitation

for several areas listed in the Table: what our journal is aiming at are the interrelationships in between. Figuratively speaking, when our Journal deals with a wall it focuses on the mortar between the individual bricks - and not so much with the bricks themselves. Thus, *Ecocycles* will not examine all subject areas in depth, but will focus on the connections between them, identifies different natural and artificial ecological cycles, and explores the possibilities of creating such cycles and linking them with each other where

and when it may be possible. There is an increasing number of artificial ecological cycles, here we mention only two: the combination of bio-energy forests as bio-filters with watering the crops with biologically cleaned waste water and using the sewage sludge for biogas production (Schroder et al., 2007) and aquaponics (a new, rapidly emerging, ecofriendly agricultural technology that integrates recirculating aquaculture with hydroponics, i.e., plant production in water, without soil. Aquaponics is highly efficient, because it uses the waste fish produce to feed the plants with nutrients, providing a symbiotic environment for producing fish and plants in a closed system (Pilinszky et al., 2015).

Thanks are due to many colleagues who have contributed to the initiation of *Ecocycles*. In particular, we are obliged to the members of the Editorial Board (listed at <http://www.ecocycles.eu/ojs/index.php?journal=Ecocycles&page=about&op=editorialTeam>) who saw the significance of the journal and decided to join in. Their proficiency in many areas of basic and applied science and their international eminence is a great input in making the journal a prestigious, internationally recognized one. We are privileged to have the unreserved support of this team.

After considering a number of options we decided that the final format of *Ecocycles* will be an open-access online journal. We adopted the Open Journal Systems framework to publish two issues a year in the beginning, with the aim of becoming a quarterly journal in three years.

Professor Tamas Komives, member of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences and founding president of the European Ecocycles Society is the Editor-in-Chief, and Dr. Sandor Nemethy of the University of Gothenburg, Sweden, is Associate Editor. Both have a long experience of editing journals and are well-known names in the fields of environmental science and education. Eminent academics and practitioners from East, West, North South, and Central Europe, as well as from other parts of the world agreed to serve as regional editors and will help identify potential contributions and provide overall guidance. Altogether, an Editorial Board with 50 outstanding members will help to

set the editorial direction of the journal.

In short, *Ecocycles*, an open access journal, freely available online, is a collaborative venture meant to stimulate dialogue and discussion about ecological cycles, an area of interest for all of us. We are looking forward to your active participation and support.

Last but not least, we wish to thank the contributors (authors and reviewers) of the inaugural issue of *Ecocycles*: we are indebted that they responded to our invitation. We strongly believe that *Ecocycles* will serve the society well, and we are looking forward to our readers' suggestions on how to improve our journal.

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